

PERFORMANCE INDICATOR EVALUATION FROM THE HUMAN RESOURCE POINT OF VIEW FOR A SALES TEAM WORKING IN PANDEMIC

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Abstract

Purpose – *The goal of this study is to evaluate the performance expressed by motivation and work security, for a sales team which worked in the pandemic.*

Methodology/approach – *A model based on a non-financial methodology was used for evaluation of performance. The level of satisfaction and motivation of workforce defined the performance level and was computed as a function of five elements. The evaluation was done for the year 2021.*

Findings – *The average value of performance was 92,82%. According with literature review, a value higher than 80% characterize a high level of performance.*

Research limitations/implications – *The analysis was done only for one sales team. It can be extended to other teams from the same company, in order to compare them and see if such a high level of performance is specific just for one team, or is similar to all teams.*

Practical implications – *The model offers a high degree of flexibility for its implementation. It is a step towards evaluation of total performance of the organization. The model provides a clear and measurable assessment of performance.*

Originality/value – *Performance indicator from the point of view of human resources allows to evaluate the performance indicator as a function of personnel fluctuation, absence due to different reasons, work satisfaction and employees degree of participation with implemented ideas.*

Key words: *motivation, pandemic, performance, satisfaction.*

Introduction

The labor markets were strongly affected by the Covid pandemic. There were many restrictions at country and world level. Many national lockdowns generated perturbations at travel and work level. It was considered more secure to work from home and to decrease the contact with the customers. Some industries were able to perform inside of this framework, but other registered a decrease or collapse. There were implemented short time labor compensation schemes. The job insecurity generated confusion, depression and a transition to the more secured jobs (IZA, 2022).

Some jobs changed their full-time status. The immigrants took over the job loss at higher level than the nationals, in majority of developed countries. A very interesting fact is that education and not gender was the border for the people who remained at their jobs. (Goldin, 2022). Many managers adopted flexible work policies. More women had remote work than men. Due to gender equity issues, it is important to promote hybrid schedule also for men. The economic inactivity represent the number of persons who not work and who do not search for a job. It increase, as well as the unemployment increased. (Powel et al, 2022). Job retention schemes were designed at country level but also in many organizations which understood how important is to keep the qualified people. All these aspects strongly affected the performance at human resource level.

Labor performance in pandemic

The crisis situations strength the importance of a well done labor force assessment from the performance point of view. The remote and hybrid work made difficult the evaluation. The boundary

between job and home became fuzzy. The Society of Human Resource Management (SHRM) underlined some approaches of performance evaluation in pandemic: just in time feedback replaces traditional performance evaluation and the results are more important than the process. The communication role became more important in the team, being expected information satisfaction level. (Miller, 2022)

Another change generated by Covid was the periodicity of evaluation, less firms practicing the human resource performance evaluation. Other companies implemented different evaluation criteria or different weight for the performance features. A study done in Czech republic revealed that if before pandemic about one third of the companies proceeded a yearly performance evaluation, after Covid only about one quarter are doing it. (Cemerikova, 2022). Last but not least, the employee loyalty changed a lot. A great extent of the number of resignations was noticed. People reconsider their life and shift from job orientation to the family and private life orientation (Baird, 2020).

The Romanian labor market was affected by pandemic. Many measures were implemented by the government for limiting the spread of Covid. A greater level of unemployment occurred in 2020 in comparison with 2019. Mentality of employees changed a lot. The workers from closed sectors shifted to new jobs in other fields. They search for more jobs which offer health insurance and remote work. (Radulescu, 2020)

Measuring performance through function of motivation and security at job

The literature review presents many attempts to model the organizational performance. The most common methods of performance evaluation are using the financial approach and the quality approach. Nowadays the performance evaluation is not limited at financial elements, the non-financial one being added from different activities and processes performed in the organization. (Cooper D., 2019). This fact is explain by the fact than achieving the proposed financial performance does not assure the fulfilling of the other objectives (Borza M., 2017).

The aspects regarding the performance at human resource level are listed among the non-financial methodologies. A higher competitiveness at company level assumes the existence of a performance measurement system. This study has as starting point the model proposed by Fecete and Nedelcu in 2019. The level of satisfaction and motivation of workforce (SMW) allow to evaluate the performance. The model allow a high degree of flexibility in its implementation. The weight of each element from the performance function was calculated using the method of specialists.

The level of satisfaction and motivation of workforce (SMW) is a function of personnel fluctuation, work satisfaction, absence generated by sickness, degree of participation with ideas, number of days of absence due to work accidents.

$$SMW = a \times PF + b \times WS + c \times ABSS + d \times DPI + e \times ABSA \quad [1]$$

SMW - satisfaction and motivation of workforce;

PF - fluctuation of personnel;

WS - work satisfaction;

ABSS - absence due to sickness;

DPI - degree of participations with ideas;

ABSA - absence due to accidents produced at work;

a, b, c, d, e - the weight associated with each element.

The fluctuation of personnel (PF) is defined as the ratio between the number of personnel which left the company and total number of personnel. The ratio of calculated index to the planned index of fluctuation will be included in the performance formula.

$$PF = \frac{PL}{TP} \times 100 \quad [2]$$

PF - personnel fluctuation;

PL - personnel left;

TP - total number of personnel.

The value of work satisfaction (WS) is evaluated using qualitative and quantitative methods. It is measured in percentages and percentage deviation from the planned value will be used for SMW calculus.

Absence because of sickness (ABSS) is computed with the following formula. The fraction of calculated absence because of sickness and its planned value will be implemented in the performance index SMW.

$$ABSS = \frac{MABS}{MWD \times NP} \times 100 \quad [3]$$

ABSS - absence because of sickness;
MABS - number of medical absence days;
MWD - number of monthly working days;
NP – number of personnel in the analyzed month.

The degree of participation with improvement and implemented ideas (DPI) is calculated as the number of workers who generated an accepted and implemented idea for job improvement divided at the total number of workers from that department. The same as in the case of previous elements, the calculated degree of participation will be divided at the intended value.

$$DPI = \frac{NWI}{DNW} \quad [4]$$

DPI - degree of participation with improvement and implemented ideas;
NWI - number of workers who generated an accepted and implemented idea;
DNW - total number of workers from that department.

The absence due to accidents produced at work (ABSA) is computed as the ratio between the number of days when the person does not work because of a work accident and the number of worked days in that month. The value obtained by calculus will be reported to the targeted value and included in the final formula of performance index SMW.

$$ABSA = \frac{NDA}{NWD} \quad [5]$$

ABSA - absence due to accidents produced at work;
NDA - number of days when the person does not work because of a work accident;
NWD - number of worked days.

The initial model selected from the literature review included the risk matrix as an additional element in the equation of performance index. This risk matrix uses the minimum value among the number of measures taken in the last twelve months, number of measures realized older than one year and accomplishment of risk one measures. This study does not use the risk matrix because there is no risk matrix designed for the sales team.

The performance can take values in the interval one to ten. A value between one and five defines the area of nonperformance. A medium performance is given by values in the interval five to eight. Higher values than eight shows a great performance.

Performance evaluation for a sales team

The sales team was dimensioned at fifteen persons but because of the pandemic its size had fluctuation. The team sales auto parts and covers the area of some counties from Transylvania. Due to confidentiality reasons, the name of the company is not revealed. The team is dedicated for both individual and organizational customers. The team members worked either from the office or online from home. They could give support to their previous customers as well as bringing new ones. The time interval for the analysis was the year 2021. There were different types of restrictions and medical regulations generated by Covid pandemic.

The first step for performance evaluation was to calculate the weight for each element from the formula. This was done using the method of specialists. The specialists were the team managers and the sales manager. There were five teams. Each specialist gave a grade from one to ten for each element. The weight of the element was computed as the ratio between the score obtained by an element and the total score.

Table 1: Score obtained by elements

	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6
PF	5	4	8	6	9	7
WS	7	2	4	5	5	6
ABSS	8	9	4	5	4	4
DPI	3	2	4	4	3	2
ABSA	5	5	4	3	1	2

$$a = \frac{39}{140} = 0.278$$

$$b = \frac{29}{140} = 0.207$$

$$c = \frac{34}{140} = 0.242$$

$$d = \frac{18}{140} = 0.128$$

$$e = \frac{20}{140} = 0.142$$

The monthly values of the five elements which define the performance expressed as satisfaction and motivation of workforce are listed in the subsequent table.

$$SMW = a \times PF + b \times WS + c \times ABSS + d \times DPI + e \times ABSA$$

Table 2: Calculation of Performance (SMW). [%]

	PF	WS	ABSS	DPI	ABSA	SMW
January	95	94	96	82	100	94,07857
February	98	96	98	76	94	94,18571
March	100	98	100	10	100	88,01429
April	86	100	100	44	87	87,04286
May	94	100	100	12	80	84,15714
June	100	92	100	62	100	93,45714
July	100	94	100	25	100	89,11429
August	100	90	100	91	100	96,77143
September	98	95	94	94	96	95,60714
October	92	98	96	100	93	95,38571
November	100	93	100	100	100	98,55
December	100	88	100	100	100	97,51429

The graphical representation of performance is illustrated in figure 1.

Figure 1: Monthly evolution of performance

The average value of performance is 92.82 %. This positions the sales team the level of high performance. The objectives are well scheduled and known by the team members.

Discussion and conclusions

The evaluation of performance by using satisfaction and motivation of workforce was done for a sales team which worked in pandemic. The analysis covered the year 2021. It considered five elements which describe the performance level: personnel fluctuation, work satisfaction, absence generated by sickness, degree of participation with ideas, number of days of absence due to work accidents. The value of 92,82% shows a high performance level.

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